

Pentachloro Cerate(III) Complexes of Pyridinium and Related Cations

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The pentachloro cerate(III) complexes of pyridinium and related cations, having the general formula $(BH)_2CeCl_5$ (where B=pyridine, 2-picoline, 3-picoline, 4-picoline, quinoline, isoquinoline, piperidine, morpholine, aniline, diethylamine or triethylamine), were prepared by the passage of hydrogen chloride gas through the solution of cerium(III) chloride containing the required base. These compounds were characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility and infrared spectra. The mode of decomposition was examined by TGA studies.

THE complex halides form a fascinating area of research, particularly from spectroscopic point of view because of their structural simplicity. Much work has been done on the complex halides and oxyhalides of the early transition series (titanium, vanadium and uranium sub groups) and rhenium in non-aqueous media¹. Hexachloro cerate(IV) complexes of pyridinium² and tetraethylammonium cations³ are known. Complex halides have been used as precursors in the synthesis of other compounds such as cerium(IV) alkoxides from dipyridinium cerium(IV) hexachloride³. There is no reference in literature about the preparation and characterization of pentachloro cerate(III) complexes of pyridinium and related cations. Hence, it was thought desirable to synthesize and characterize these complexes. These complexes were prepared from cerium(III) chloride, the corresponding base and hydrochloric acid in water. The compounds are hygroscopic in nature and are insoluble in almost all common organic solvents except methanol and dimethylformide. Analytical data, molar conductance and magnetic susceptibility values of these complexes are summarized in Table 1.

Experimental

The bases used were purified by fractional distillation after keeping them over potassium hydroxide pellets overnight. Cerium(III) chloride heptahydrate (Indian Rare Earths Ltd.) was made anhydrous by heating it upto 350° and then immediately taking it in a high vacuum desiccator⁴. Molar conductance of the complexes was determined on their millimolar solutions in methanol by using an Elico Conductivity Bridge, Type CM 82T. Magnetic measurements of the complexes were carried out at room temperature by the Gouy technique using $Hg[Co(NCS)_4]$ as calibrant. The infrared spectra of the complexes over the region 4000-200 cm^{-1} were recorded on a Perkin Elmer-621 infrared grating spectrophotometer using nujol

mu. Thermal analyses of the complexes at the heating rate of 10°/min were carried out by thermogravimetry on thermorecording balance (Stanton Instruments, Model No-750) and at the rate of 7°/min on Setaram thermoanalyser G.70 Leyom, France.

Preparation of (pyridine H)₂CeCl₅: Anhydrous hydrogen chloride gas was passed through a solution of cerium(III) chloride (0.98 g; 0.004 mole) in water (100 ml) until it became saturated (1.30 hr). Pyridine (0.63 g; 0.008 mole) was added and more hydrogen chloride gas was passed through the mixture (~ 40 min). The solution was concentrated to 10 ml which upon cooling gave a white compound. It was repeatedly washed with acetone and dried. The other compounds were prepared using the same procedure.

Analyses: Cerium was determined gravimetrically as CeO₂. Chlorine was estimated as silver chloride. Carbon and hydrogen were determined by microanalytical methods.

Results and Discussion

The method of preparation of the complexes is analogous to the preparation of dipyridinium iron(III) pentachloride⁵.

Molar conductance: The molar conductance values (in methanol) of these complexes lie in the range 178-191 $ohm^{-1} cm^2 mole^{-1}$ indicating these complexes to be 1 : 2 electrolytes.

Magnetic moments: The magnetic moment values lie in the range 2.50-2.58 B.M. which indicate that the complexes are paramagnetic in nature. The observed magnetic moments are very close to that of free ion value of cerium(III) as given by VanVleck⁶ and Hund⁷. This consistency in the observed magnetic moments of the complexes shows that hardly any interaction takes place between the orbitals of the metal ion and those of ligands

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC DATA OF PENTACHLORO CERATE(III) COMPLEXES OF PYRIDINIUM AND RELATED CATIONS

Compound	Analysis% ; Found(Calcd.)				Molar conductance mole ⁻¹ ohm ⁻¹ cm ²	μ_{eff} B.M.
	Carbon	Hydrogen	Cerium	Chloride		
(Pyridine H) ₂ CeCl ₅	25.11 (25.15)	2.52 (2.53)	28.97 (29.84)	36.84 (37.12)	189.15	2.50
(2-Picoline H) ₂ CeCl ₅	28.31 (28.50)	3.14 (3.19)	27.54 (27.71)	34.97 (35.06)	191.33	2.52
(3-Picoline H) ₂ CeCl ₅	28.19 (28.50)	3.16 (3.19)	27.63 (27.71)	34.97 (35.06)	187.42	2.52
(4-Picoline H) ₂ CeCl ₅	28.42 (28.50)	3.18 (3.19)	27.51 (27.71)	34.93 (35.06)	187.53	2.56
(Quinoline H) ₂ CeCl ₅	37.37 (37.42)	2.75 (2.79)	24.06 (24.26)	30.28 (30.68)	191.27	2.58
(Isoquinoline H) ₂ CeCl ₅	37.28 (37.42)	2.76 (2.79)	24.12 (24.26)	30.51 (30.68)	188.29	2.52
(Piperidine H) ₂ CeCl ₅	24.32 (24.52)	4.88 (4.94)	28.35 (28.61)	36.27 (36.20)	191.15	2.54
(Morpholine H) ₂ CeCl ₅	19.20 (19.46)	4.02 (4.08)	28.10 (28.39)	35.45 (35.91)	180.85	2.54
(Aniline H) ₂ CeCl ₅	28.30 (28.50)	3.14 (3.19)	27.30 (27.71)	35.03 (35.06)	187.12	2.51
(Diethylamine H) ₂ CeCl ₅	20.29 (20.63)	5.16 (5.19)	30.02 (30.09)	37.84 (38.07)	184.72	2.52
(Triethylamine H) ₂ CeCl ₅	27.24 (27.62)	6.15 (6.18)	26.60 (26.86)	33.64 (33.97)	178.67	2.55

suggesting that bonding in these complexes remains electrostatic.

Infrared spectra : Pyridinium^{8,9}, 2-picolinium, 3-picolinium, 4-picolinium¹⁰, quinolinium and isoquinolinium¹¹ cations in their respective complexes under investigation have shown the stretching vibrations near 1630, 1600, 1530, 1485 and 1370 cm⁻¹. The bands near 1320, 1240, 1195, 1155, 1050 and 1025 cm⁻¹ are exhibited by the complexes and are interpreted for hydrogen in-plane deformations. A band near 1010 cm⁻¹ represents the symmetric ring breathing mode while the bands near 745 and 690 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ring bending mode and out-of-plane hydrogen deformations, respectively. A band near 1245 cm⁻¹ is considered for N-H group. The triethylammonium cation exhibits >NH⁺ frequency at 2540 cm⁻¹. The deformational mode of the triethylammonium ion appears at 1620 cm⁻¹¹². Thus, the infrared spectral studies confirm the presence of the pyridinium, 2-picolinium, 3-picolinium, 4-picolinium, quinolinium, isoquinolinium and triethylammonium cations in the complexes. The infrared spectrum of (aniline H)₂CeCl₅ shows absorptions at 1620 and 1300 cm⁻¹ due to -NH₂⁺ deformation, asymmetric and symmetric, respectively. There appears a peak at 815 cm⁻¹ which may be due to -NH₂⁺ rocking vibration. Piperidinium, morpholinium and diethylammonium cations¹³ in their respective complexes exhibit two NH stretching modes for asymmetrical and symmetrical vibrational frequencies near 2920 and 2840 cm⁻¹. A band near 1600 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the deformational mode of the >NH₂⁺ group. Two more bands appear near 2500 and 2400 cm⁻¹ which may be considered for >NH₂⁺ group as well. On the basis of these

frequencies, the presence of piperidinium, morpholinium and diethylammonium cations is established in these complexes.

Thermogravimetric analysis : The thermogravimetric analysis of some representative compounds has been carried out under nitrogen :

(Aniline H)₂CeCl₅ : The weight of the sample used was 27 mg. It is observed from the horizontal line on the TG curve (Fig. 1a) that the complex is thermally stable upto 200°. Above this temperature it starts decomposing abruptly and it gives a plateau at 365°. The observed weight loss (13.80 mg) corresponds fairly to the loss of two molecules of aniline and hydrogen chloride (Calcd. weight loss 13.84 mg). The formation of CeCl₃ is indicated as an intermediate which is found stable upto 440° on the TG curve. After this it starts

Fig. 1. TG Curves of (a) (Aniline H)₂CeCl₅, (b) (Piperidine H)₂CeCl₅ and (c) (Morpholine H)₂CeCl₅ under N₂. The samples were heated at 7°/min. Weight of the sample taken : (a) 27.0 mg, (b) 28.0 mg and (c) 30.0 mg.

decomposing gradually and finally reaches a constant level at 700°. The observed weight loss (19.45 mg) is attributed to the formation of cerium metal as an end product (Calcd. weight loss 19.52 mg).

(*Piperidine H*)₂CeCl₅: The complex is stable upto 80° as evident from the TG curve (Fig. 1b). The formation of CeCl₃ as an intermediate is indicated at 390° (weight loss, Found: 14.0 mg; Calcd. 13.9 mg) and finally cerium metal is formed at 700° (weight loss, Found: 20.0 mg; Calcd. 19.99 mg).

Fig. 2. TG Curve of (Triethylamine H)₂CeCl₅ under N₂. The sample was heated at 10°/min. Weight of the sample taken = 5.0 mg.

(*Morpholine H*)₂CeCl₅: TG curve (Fig. 1c) shows the complex to be thermally stable upto 80°. The formation of CeCl₃ as an intermediate is considered (weight loss, Found: 15 mg; Calcd. 15.02 mg). The final weight loss at 720° (21.6 mg) is attributed to the formation of cerium metal (Calcd. weight loss 21.48 mg).

(*Triethylamine H*)₂CeCl₅: Horizontal line on TG curve (Fig. 2) shows the stability of the complex upto 70°. At 301°, CeCl₃ as an intermediate is observed (weight loss, Found: 2.65 mg; Calcd. 2.64 mg). Finally, the cerium metal is formed at 690° (weight loss, Found: 3.55 mg; Calcd. 3.66 mg).

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